

[white paper]

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Proofs of Theorems in Topology

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Abstract

We prove some theorems in topology using the fewest number of symbols at each step. Our purpose is pedagogical.

keywords: proofs, theorems, topology

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/wn24y/download>
<https://zenodo.org/record/6622005>

Introduction

1. [1–3]
2. $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$; $\mathbb{N}^+ = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$
3. $(A \vdash B) := (A \text{ proves } B)$
4. $(A \vdash B \vdash C) := (A \text{ proves } B \text{ and } B \text{ proves } C)$
5. $(A := B) \equiv (A \text{ is defined by } B)$

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6. $(x =_\ell y) \equiv (\text{let } x \text{ be } y)$
7. $(xR_\ell A) \equiv (\text{let } xRA); \quad R := \text{binary relation}$
8. $\blacksquare := \text{an instance of the theorem was proved}$
9. $\square := \text{qed}$
10. $(\text{wlog } A) := \text{assume } A \text{ without loss of generality}$
11. $(x \in A, B) \equiv ((x \in A) \wedge (x \in B))$
12. $(X \subseteq A, B) \equiv ((X \subseteq A) \wedge (X \subseteq B))$
13. $\exists_n := \text{there is a finite number}$
14. $(? \vdash A) := \text{we will prove } A$

Cauchy sequence bounded by a rational number

1. Theorem

$\forall (x_n) : (x_n) \equiv \text{Cauchy sequence of rational numbers} \rightarrow$
 $\rightarrow (x_n) \equiv \text{bounded by } q \in \mathbb{Q}$

2. Definitions

3. $(x_n) := \text{rational-valued sequence}$

4. $(x_n) \equiv \text{Cauchy sequence if}$

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{N}^+, \exists K \in \mathbb{N}, m, n \in \mathbb{N}^+ : m \geq n > K \rightarrow |x_m - x_n| < \frac{1}{k}$$

5. Triangle Inequality: $\forall x, y \in \mathbb{Q} : |x + y| \leq |x| + |y|$

6. Proof

7. $(x_n) =_\ell$ Cauchy sequence of rational numbers
8. $(5) \vdash |x_m| = |(x_m - x_n) + x_n| \leq |x_m - x_n| + |x_n|$
9. $k =_\ell 1$
10. $(4,7,9) \vdash m \geq n > K \rightarrow |x_m| \leq |x_m - x_n| + |x_n| < 1 + |x_n|$
11. $m \geq n > K \rightarrow |x_m| < 1 + |x_n|$
12. $n =_\ell K + 1$
13. $m > K \rightarrow |x_m| < 1 + |x_{K+1}|$
14. $M =_\ell \max\{|x_0|, |x_1|, \dots, |x_K|, |x_{K+1}|\}$
15. $\forall m \in \mathbb{N}, |x_m| \leq M$ □

Rationals and Reals have the Archimedean Property

1. Theorem

$\mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}$ has the Archimedean Property

2. Definitions

3.

$(\forall x \in F \exists n \in \mathbb{N} : n > x) \rightarrow (F \text{ has the Archimedean Property})$

4. $F :=$ ordered field

5. (3) means that $\mathbb{N}$ is *unbounded* in F .

6. $(x_n) \equiv$ Cauchy sequence if

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{N}^+, \exists K \in \mathbb{N}, m, n \in \mathbb{N}^+ : m \geq n > K \rightarrow |x_m - x_n| < \frac{1}{k}$$

7. $\mathbb{R} = \{[(x_n)] \mid (x_n) \equiv \text{Cauchy sequence of } q \in \mathbb{Q}\}$
8. $\sim :=$ equivalence relation
9. $(x \in S) \rightarrow [x] = \{y \in S \mid x \sim y\}$
10. $[x] :=$ equivalence class of x
11. $(f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow A) \equiv$ infinite sequence
12. $(f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow X, f(n) = x_n) \rightarrow (f := (x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} := (x_n))$
13. Proof for $\mathbb{Q}$
14. $q \in \mathbb{Q}$ (arbitrary)
15. $<$ is transitive
16. case 1: $(15) \vdash q \leq 0, 0 < 1 \rightarrow q < 1$
17. case 2: $q > 0, \exists a, b \in \mathbb{Z}^+ : q = \frac{a}{b}$
18. $a + 1 - q = (a + 1) - \frac{a}{b} = \frac{a(b - 1) + b}{b}$
19. $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \vdash b - 1 \geq 0 \vdash a(b - 1) \geq 0$
20. $a(b - 1) + b \geq 0 + b > 0$
21. $(a + 1) - \frac{a}{b} = \frac{a(b - 1) + b}{b} > 0$
22. $(a + 1) > \frac{a}{b} = q$
23. $(a, 1 \in \mathbb{N}; \mathbb{N} \text{ is closed under addition}) \vdash a + 1 \in \mathbb{N}$
24. $(14, 23) \vdash \forall q \in \mathbb{Q} \exists n \in \mathbb{N} : n > q$ □
25. Proof (by contradiction) for $\mathbb{R}$

26. $(x_n) :=$ Cauchy sequence
27. $(7) \vdash [(x_n)] \in \mathbb{R}$
28. $[(i)] :=$ natural number $(i \in \mathbb{N})$
29. $[(x_n)] :=$ real number $(n \in \mathbb{N})$
30. Suppose (toward contradiction): $\forall i \in \mathbb{N}, [(i)] \leq [(x_n)]$.
31. $(30) \vdash \forall i \in \mathbb{N}, \exists K_i \in \mathbb{N} : n > K_i \rightarrow i \leq x_n$
32. $(1,26) \vdash \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, x_n \leq M \in \mathbb{Q}$
33. $i \in_{\ell} \mathbb{N}$ (arbitrary), choose $K_i : n > K_i \rightarrow i \leq x_n$
34. $i \leq x_n, x_n \leq M, \leq$ is transitive $\vdash i \leq M \in \mathbb{Q}$
35. $(34) \vdash \mathbb{N} \equiv$ bounded by $M \in \mathbb{Q}$
36. (35) contradicts (24) .
37. $\forall x \in \mathbb{R} \exists n \in \mathbb{N} : n > x$ □

Density Theorem

1. Theorem

$$(x, y \in \mathbb{R}, x < y) \rightarrow (\exists q \in \mathbb{Q} : x < q < y)$$

2. Definitions

3. WOP := Well Ordering Principle

4.

$$(\forall x \in F \exists n \in \mathbb{N} : n > x) \rightarrow (F \text{ has the Archimedean Property})$$

5. Lemma

$\mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}$ has the Archimedean Property

6. Proof
7. $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$
8. Case 1: $0 \leq x < y$
9. $z = y - x = y + (-x)$
10. $\mathbb{R}$ has the additive inverse property, $\mathbb{R}$ is closed under addition $\vdash z \in \mathbb{R}$
11. $(8, 9) \vdash z > 0$
12. $(4, 5) \vdash \exists n \in \mathbb{N} : n > \frac{1}{z}$
13. $\frac{1}{n} < z$
14. $(4, 5) \vdash \exists m \in \mathbb{N} : m > nx$
15. $\frac{m}{n} > x$
16. $\left\{ m \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{m}{n} > x \right\} \neq \emptyset$
17. $(3) \vdash \left\{ m \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{m}{n} > x \right\}$ has a least element k
18. $x \geq 0, n > 0, k > 0$
19. $k \equiv \text{least } \mathbb{N} : \frac{k}{n} > x$
20. $k - 1 \in \mathbb{N}, \frac{k - 1}{n} \leq x$
21. $\frac{k}{n} - \frac{1}{n} \leq x$
22. $(9, 13, 21) \vdash \frac{k}{n} \leq x + \frac{1}{n} < x + z = x + (y - x) = y$

23. $(19,22) \vdash x < \frac{k}{n} < y$
24. $k, n \in \mathbb{N}; \frac{k}{n} \in \mathbb{Q} \quad \blacksquare$
25. Case 2: $x < 0$ and $x < y$
26. $(4,5) \vdash \exists t \in \mathbb{N} : t > -x$
27. $(25,26) \vdash 0 < x + t < y + t$
28. $(8,23,24,27) \vdash \exists q \in \mathbb{Q} : x + t < q < y + t$
29. $x < q - t < y$
30. $t \in \mathbb{N}, -t \in \mathbb{Z}$
31. $\mathbb{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{Q}, -t \in \mathbb{Q}$
32. $q, -t \in \mathbb{Q}$
33. $\mathbb{Q} \equiv$ closed under addition
34. $q' = q - t = q + (-t) \in \mathbb{Q}$
35. $\exists q' \in \mathbb{Q} : x < q' < y \quad \blacksquare$
36. $(24,35) \vdash (1)$ □

Infinite interval open in $\mathbb{R}$

1. Theorem

$$a \in \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (a, \infty) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

2. $(a, \infty) :=$ infinite open interval in $\mathbb{R}$

3. Definitions

4.

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

5.

$$\mathcal{X} := \text{open set in } Y$$

$$(i) \mathcal{X} \subseteq Y$$

$$(ii) \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathcal{X}$$

6.

$$\forall (a, b) : (a, b) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

7. $X, Y := \text{sets}$

8. $(a, b) := \text{open interval in } \mathbb{R}$

9. Proof

$$10. x \in_{\ell} (a, \infty), b =_{\ell} x + 1.$$

$$11. x \in (a, \infty) \vdash x > a$$

$$12. b = x + 1 \vdash b - x = 1 > 0 \vdash b > x$$

$$13. (11,12) \vdash a < x < b \vdash x \in (a, b)$$

$$14. (a, b) \subseteq (a, \infty)$$

$$15. x \text{ arbitrary} \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{R} : (a, x + 1) \subseteq (a, \infty)$$

$$16. (6) \vdash (a, x + 1) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

$$17. (15,16) \vdash (a, \infty) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

□

Empty set and $\mathbb{R}$ open in $\mathbb{R}$

1. Theorem

$\emptyset, \mathbb{R} \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$

2. Definitions

3.

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

4.

$\mathcal{X} := \text{open set in } Y$

(i) $\mathcal{X} \subseteq Y$

(ii) $\forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathcal{X}$

5.

$\forall (a, b) : (a, b) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$

6. $X, Y := \text{sets}$

7. $(a, b) := \text{open interval in } \mathbb{R}$

8. Proof

9. $\emptyset \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$ (vacuously true) □

10. $x \in_{\ell} \mathbb{R}$ arbitrary

11. $x \in (x - 1, x + 1) \vdash (x - 1, x + 1) \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

12. $(a, b) := \text{open interval}$

13. $(10, 11) \vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{R} : \exists (a, b), x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

14. $(5, 13) \vdash \mathbb{R} \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$ □

Subset of $\mathbb{R}$, Open in $\mathbb{R}$

1. Theorem

$$(X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (\forall x \in X, \exists c > 0, c \in \mathbb{R} : (x - c, x + c) \subseteq X)$$

2. $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

3. $(x - c, x + c) :=$ open interval in $\mathbb{R}$

4. Definitions

5.

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

6.

$$\mathcal{X} := \text{open set in } Y$$

$$(i) \mathcal{X} \subseteq Y$$

$$(ii) \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathcal{X}$$

7.

$$\forall (a, b) : (a, b) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

8. $X, Y :=$ sets

9. $(a, b) :=$ open interval in $\mathbb{R}$

10. Proof

11. $(\rightarrow)$

12. $X \subseteq_{\ell} \mathbb{R}, X =_{\ell} \text{open in } \mathbb{R}, x \in_{\ell} \mathbb{R}.$

13. $(12) \vdash \exists (a, b) \subseteq X, x \in (a, b)$

14. $c =_{\ell} \min\{x - a, b - x\}$

15. $(14) \vdash c \leq x - a \vdash c - x \leq x - a - x \vdash c - x \leq -a \vdash x - c \geq a$

16. $c \leq b - x$
17. $x + c \leq x + b - x \vdash x + c \leq b$
18. (13) $\vdash x \in (a, b) \vdash x > a, x < b \vdash x - a > 0, b - x > 0$
19. (14,18) $\vdash c > 0 \vdash x + c > x$
20. $c > 0 \vdash -c < 0 \vdash x - c < x$
21. (15,17,19,20) $\vdash a \leq x - c < x < x + c \leq b$
22. $(x - c, x + c) \subseteq (a, b) \subseteq X$
23. $\subseteq$ is transitive
24. (22,23) $\vdash (x - c, x + c) \subseteq X$ ■
25. ($\leftarrow$)
26. $x \in \mathbb{R}, (x - c, x + c) \subseteq X, c > 0, (7) \vdash X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ is open in $\mathbb{R}$ ■
27. (24,26) $\vdash (1)$ □

Union open sets, open in $\mathbb{R}$

1. Theorem

$$A \cup B \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

2. $A, B :=$ open sets in $\mathbb{R}$

3. Definitions

4.

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

5.

$$\mathcal{X} := \text{open set in } Y$$

- (i) $\mathcal{X} \subseteq Y$
- (ii) $\forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathcal{X}$
- 6. $X, Y :=$ sets
- 7. $(a, b) :=$ open interval in $\mathbb{R}$
- 8. Proof
- 9. $A, B =_{\ell}$ open in $\mathbb{R}$; $x \in_{\ell} A \cup B$
- 10. $(x \in A) \vee (x \in B)$
- 11. wlog, assume $x \in A$
- 12. $A \equiv$ open in $\mathbb{R} \vdash \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq A$
- 13. $A \subseteq A \cup B$
- 14. $\subseteq$ is transitive
- 15. $(a, b) \subseteq A \cup B$
- 16. $A \cup B \equiv$ open in $\mathbb{R}$ □

Bounded Open Intervals

1. Theorem

$$(\forall X \subseteq \mathbb{R}, X \neq \emptyset, X := \text{open set in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (X = \bigcup B)$$

2. $B :=$ set of bounded open intervals

3. Definitions

4.

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

5.

$\mathcal{X} :=$ open set in Y

(i) $\mathcal{X} \subseteq Y$

(ii) $\forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathcal{X}$

6. $X, Y :=$ sets

7. $(a, b) :=$ open interval in $\mathbb{R}$

8. Proof

9. $X \neq \emptyset$

10. $X :=$ open in $\mathbb{R}$

11. (10) $\vdash \forall x \in X : \exists (a_x, b_x) : x \in (a_x, b_x) \subseteq X$

12. $Y =_{\ell} \{(a_x, b_x) \mid x \in X\}$

13. $x \in_{\ell} X$ arbitrary

14. (11,13) $\vdash x \in (a_x, b_x)$

15. (12) $\vdash (a_x, b_x) \in Y$

16. $x \in (a_x, b_x) \in Y \vdash x \in \cup Y$

17. (13,16) $\vdash X \subseteq \cup Y$ ■

18. $x \in_{\ell} \cup Y$ arbitrary

19. $x \in \cup Y, Y = \{(a_x, b_x) \mid x \in X\} \vdash \exists z \in X : x \in (a_z, b_z)$

20. (10,19) $\vdash x \in (a_z, b_z) \subseteq X$

21. (18,20) $\vdash x \in \cup Y \rightarrow x \in X$

22. (18,21) $\vdash \cup Y \subseteq X$ ■

23. (17,22) $\vdash X = \cup Y$

□

Intersection of open sets in $\mathbb{R}$ is open

1. Theorem

$$A \cap B \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

2. $A, B :=$ open sets in $\mathbb{R}$

3. Definitions

4.

$$(a, b) = \{x \in X \mid a < x < b\}$$

5.

$$\mathcal{X} := \text{open set in } Y$$

$$(i) \mathcal{X} \subseteq Y$$

$$(ii) \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathcal{X}$$

6. $X, Y :=$ sets

7. $(a, b) :=$ open interval in $\mathbb{R}$

8. open $:=$ open in $\mathbb{R} :=$ open set in $\mathbb{R}$

9. Proof

10. $A, B =_{\ell}$ open in $\mathbb{R}$

11. $x \in_{\ell} A \cap B$ arbitrary

12. $x \in A, B$

13. (5), $A \equiv \text{open} \vdash \exists (a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

14. $B \equiv \text{open} \vdash \exists (c, d) : x \in (c, d) \subseteq B$

15. $C =_{\ell} (a, b) \cap (c, d) \neq \emptyset$

16. $x \in (a, b), (c, d) \vdash x \in C$

17. Lemma: $(a, b) \cap (c, d) \equiv \emptyset \vee$ (open interval in $\mathbb{R}$).
18. $(15,16,17) \vdash C \equiv$ open interval in $\mathbb{R}$
19. Lemma: $A \cap B \subseteq A$.
20. Lemma: $\cap$ is commutative.
21. $x \in (a, b) \subseteq A, x \in (c, d) \subseteq B, C = (a, b) \cap (c, d), A \cap B \subseteq A \vdash C \subseteq A, B$
22. Lemma: $C \subseteq A, B \rightarrow C \subseteq A \cap B$.
23. $(21,22) \vdash C \subseteq A \cap B$
24. x arbitrary, $(5,18,23) \vdash A \cap B \equiv$ open in $\mathbb{R}$ □

Intersection of Closed Sets

1. Theorem

$$A \cap B \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$$

2. $A, B :=$ closed sets in $\mathbb{R}$

3. Definitions

4.

$$(\mathbb{R} \setminus X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (X \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R})$$

5. $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

6. $\mathbb{R} \setminus X :=$ complement of X in $\mathbb{R}$

7. Proof

8. $A, B =_{\ell}$ closed in $\mathbb{R}$

9. $(4,8) \vdash \mathbb{R} \setminus A, \mathbb{R} \setminus B \equiv$ open in $\mathbb{R}$

10. Lemma

$$(X := \text{set of open subsets of } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \bigcup X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$$

11. (9,10) $\vdash (\mathbb{R} \setminus A) \cup (\mathbb{R} \setminus B) \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$

12. (4,11) $\vdash \mathbb{R} \setminus [(\mathbb{R} \setminus A) \cup (\mathbb{R} \setminus B)] \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$

13.

$$\begin{aligned} (x \in A \cap B) &\leftrightarrow (x \in A \wedge x \in B) \leftrightarrow (x \notin \mathbb{R} \setminus A \wedge x \notin \mathbb{R} \setminus B) \leftrightarrow \\ &\leftrightarrow x \notin (\mathbb{R} \setminus A) \cup (\mathbb{R} \setminus B) \leftrightarrow x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus [(\mathbb{R} \setminus A) \cup (\mathbb{R} \setminus B)] \end{aligned}$$

14. $A \cap B = \mathbb{R} \setminus [(\mathbb{R} \setminus A) \cup (\mathbb{R} \setminus B)]$

15. (12,14) $\vdash A \cap B \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$

□

Closed in $\mathbb{R}$, Accumulation Points

1. Theorem

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } C \rightarrow x \in C)$$

2. $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

3. Definitions

4.

$$\begin{aligned} x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S &\leftrightarrow \\ \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R} (a < x < b \rightarrow \exists y \in S (a < y < b \wedge y \neq x)) &\equiv \\ \equiv \text{every open interval containing } x &\text{ contains at least one point of } S \\ &\text{different from } x \end{aligned}$$

5. $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}; \quad x \in \mathbb{R}$

6. $(\mathbb{R} \setminus X \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow (X \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R})$
7. $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$
8. $\mathbb{R} \setminus X := \text{complement of } X \text{ in } \mathbb{R}$
9. Proof
10. $(\rightarrow)$
11. Assume: C closed in $\mathbb{R}$.
12. $\mathbb{R} \setminus C \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$
13. $x \notin C$ arbitrary
14. $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus C$
15. (12) $\vdash \exists(a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{R} \setminus C$
16. Suppose $y \in (a, b)$ arbitrary.
17. (16), $(a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{R} \setminus C \vdash y \notin C$
18. (4,17) $\vdash x \neq \text{accumulation point of } C$
19. (13,18) $\vdash x \notin C \rightarrow x \neq \text{accumulation point of } C$
20. contrapositive of (19): $(x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } C) \rightarrow (x \in C)$ ■
21. $(\leftarrow)$
22. Assume: $(x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } C) \rightarrow (x \in C)$.
23. $\emptyset \equiv \text{open in } \mathbb{R}$
24. Assume: $\mathbb{R} \setminus C \neq \emptyset$.
25. contrapositive of (22): $(x \notin C) \rightarrow (x \neq \text{accumulation point of } C)$

26. $x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus C \vdash x \notin C$
27. $(22,25,26) \vdash x \neq$ accumulation point of C
28. $(4,27) \vdash \exists(a,b) : x \in (a,b), (a,b) \cap C = \emptyset$
29. $(a,b) \subseteq \mathbb{R} \setminus C$
30. x arbitrary, $\mathbb{R} \setminus C \equiv$ open in $\mathbb{R}$, $C \equiv$ closed in $\mathbb{R}$ □

Closure, Accumulation Point, Closed in $\mathbb{R}$

Theorems

1.

$$S \subseteq \overline{S}$$

2.

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}, S \subseteq C) \rightarrow (\overline{S} \subseteq C)$$

3.

$$\overline{S} = S \cup \{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\}$$

4.

$$(S \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (S = \overline{S})$$

5.

$$(x \in \overline{S}) \leftrightarrow \forall X (x \in X \rightarrow \exists s \in X)$$

6. $s \in S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

7. $\overline{S} :=$ closure of S in $\mathbb{R}$

8. $X :=$ open interval

9. Definitions

10.

$$\overline{S} = \bigcap \{C \mid S \subseteq C, C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}\}$$

11. $\overline{S} :=$ closure of S in $\mathbb{R}$

12.

$$\begin{aligned} x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S &\leftrightarrow \\ \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R} (a < x < b \rightarrow \exists y \in S (a < y < b \wedge y \neq x)) &\equiv \\ \equiv \text{every open interval containing } x \text{ contains at least one point of } S & \\ &\text{different from } x \end{aligned}$$

13. $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}; \quad x \in \mathbb{R}$

14. Proof of (1),

$$S \subseteq \overline{S}$$

15. $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

16. $x \in_{\ell} S$ arbitrary

17. $C =_{\ell}$ closed in $\mathbb{R}$

18. Lemma

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } C \rightarrow x \in C)$$

19. $C \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

20. (16) $\vdash S \subseteq C \rightarrow x \in C$

21. $x \in C \vdash x \in \bigcap \{C \mid S \subseteq C, C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}\} = \overline{S}$

22. $x \in \overline{S}$

23. (16,22) $\vdash \forall x(x \in S \rightarrow x \in \overline{S}) \vdash S \subseteq \overline{S}$

□

24. Proof of (2),

$$(C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}, S \subseteq C) \rightarrow (\overline{S} \subseteq C)$$

25. $C =_{\ell}$ closed in $\mathbb{R}$, $S \subseteq_{\ell} C$

26. $x \in_{\ell} \overline{S}$ arbitrary

27. (10,26) $\vdash x \in C$

28. (26,27) $\vdash \forall x(x \in \overline{S} \rightarrow x \in C)$

29. $\overline{S} \subseteq C$ ■

30. Proof of (3),

$$\overline{S} = S \cup \{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\}$$

31. $C =_{\ell} S \cup \{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\}$

32. (10) $\vdash \overline{S} \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$

33. ? $\vdash (C \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R})$

34. $x =_{\ell}$ accumulation point of C

35. $x \in_{\ell} (a, b)$

36. $y \in_{\ell} C$, $y \in_{\ell} (a, b)$, $y \neq_{\ell} x$

37. case 1: $x < y$

38. $y \in C \vdash (y \in S) \vee (y \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S)$

39. $y \in S \vdash \exists z \in S : z \in (x, b)$

40. $y \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S \vdash \exists z \in S : z \in (x, b)$

41. case 2: $x > y \vdash \exists z \in S : z \in (a, x)$

42. (40,41), $z \neq x \vdash x :=$ accumulation point of S
43. (31,34,42) $\vdash x \in C$
44. x arbitrary $\vdash \forall x \in \mathbb{R} : (x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } C) \rightarrow x \in C$
45. (18,44) $\vdash C \equiv$ closed in $\mathbb{R}$ ■
46. ? $\vdash \overline{S} \subseteq C$
47. (31) $\vdash S \subseteq C$
48. (2,45,47) $\vdash \overline{S} \subseteq C$ ■
49. ? $\vdash C \subseteq \overline{S}$
50. suppose $x \notin \overline{S}$
51. (1,50) $\vdash x \notin S$
52. $\overline{S} \equiv$ closed in $\mathbb{R}$
53. $\mathbb{R} \setminus \overline{S} \equiv$ open in $\mathbb{R}$
54. $x \notin \overline{S} \vdash x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \overline{S}$
55. (53,54) $\vdash \exists(a, b) : x \in (a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{R} \setminus \overline{S}$
56. (1) $\vdash S \subseteq \overline{S} \vdash \mathbb{R} \setminus \overline{S} \subseteq \mathbb{R} \setminus S$
57. $\subseteq$ is transitive
58. (55,56,57) $\vdash (a, b) \subseteq \mathbb{R} \setminus S$
59. (12,58) $\vdash x \not\equiv$ accumulation point of S
60. (51,59) $\vdash x \notin C$
61. $x \notin \overline{S}$ arbitrary, (60) $\vdash \forall x(x \in \overline{S} \rightarrow x \notin C)$
62. contrapositive of (61) $\vdash \forall x(x \in C \rightarrow x \in \overline{S})$

63. $(62) \vdash C \subseteq \overline{S}$ ■

64. $(48,63) \vdash \overline{S} = C$

□

65. Proof of (4),

$$(S \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}) \leftrightarrow (S = \overline{S})$$

66. $(\rightarrow)$

67. assume S closed in $\mathbb{R}$

68. $(1) \equiv (S \subseteq \overline{S})$

69. $(2) \equiv ((S \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}, S \subseteq S) \rightarrow (\overline{S} \subseteq S))$

70. $(1,2,67) \vdash \overline{S} \subseteq S$

71. $(1,70) \vdash S = \overline{S}$ ■

72. $(\leftarrow)$

73. assume $S = \overline{S}$

74. $\overline{S} \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$

75. $(73,74) \vdash S \equiv \text{closed in } \mathbb{R}$ ■

76. $(71,75) \vdash (4)$

77. Proof of (5),

$$(x \in \overline{S}) \leftrightarrow \forall X (x \in X \rightarrow \exists s \in X)$$

78. $s \in S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$

79. $\overline{S} := \text{closure of } S \text{ in } \mathbb{R}$

80. $X := \text{open interval}$

81. $(\rightarrow)$

82. $x \in_{\ell} \overline{S}$
83. $x \in_{\ell} (a, b)$
84. (3) $\equiv (\overline{S} = S \cup \{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\})$
85. (3,82) $\vdash (x \in S) \vee (x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S)$
86. case 1: $x \in S$
87. $x \in (a, b)$
88. $x \in S, (a, b) \vdash (x \in \overline{S}) \rightarrow \forall X(x \in X \wedge \exists s \in X)$; $X \equiv \text{open interval}$ ■
89. case 2: $x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S$
90. (12,89) $\vdash \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R}(x \in (a, b) \rightarrow \exists y \in S(y \in (a, b), y \neq x))$ ■
91. ($\leftarrow$)
92. assume: $\forall X(x \in X \rightarrow \exists s \in X)$; $s \in S \subseteq \mathbb{R}$; $X := \text{open interval in } \mathbb{R}$
93. (1) $\equiv (S \subseteq \overline{S})$
94. ? $\vdash x \in \overline{S}$
95. case 1: $x \in S$
96. (1) $\vdash x \in \overline{S}$ ■
97. case 2: $x \notin S$
98. (92,97) $\vdash \forall X(x \in X \rightarrow \exists s \in S, s \neq x)$
99. (12,98) $\vdash x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S$
100. (3) $\equiv (\overline{S} = S \cup \{x \in \mathbb{R} \mid x \equiv \text{accumulation point of } S\})$
101. (3,99) $\vdash x \in \overline{S}$ ■
102. (92,96,101) $\vdash (5)$ □

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Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [4, 5].

Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.

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The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [6, 7].

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